

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES

Scientific and Academy Journal

Print ISSN 2222-7288

Online ISSN 2518-5551

IMPACT FACTOR VALUE OF 2.329

Vol. (46/2)–SPECIAL ISSUE JULY-2025

**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
GOVERNANCE IN THE UKRAINIAN EXPERIENCE**

**15. Legal Aspects of Penalties for Public Asset
Misuse: Challenges of Law Enforcement
studying. By IGOR PARYZKYI. and others. p. 299.**

CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH-DENMARK

AALBORG ACADEMY OF SCIENCES – DENMARK

<http://journal-law.com/>

journallaw1@yahoo.co

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

P.ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

VOL. 45-2-ISSUE 3-June 2025 -Special issue

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES

SCIENTIFIC AND ACADEMY JOURNAL

Print ISSN 2222-7288

Online ISSN 2518-5551

IMPACT FACTOR VALUE OF 2.701

VOL. (46/2) SPECIAL ISSUE JULY 2025

FIRST EDITION 2011

SPECIAL ISSUE

**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
GOVERNANCE IN THE UKRAINIAN EXPERIENCE
A GROUP OF UNIVERSITY GRADUATES IN UKRAINE
PREPARED**

**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
FACULTY OF LAW - ACADEMY OF THE AALBORG – DENMARK**

<http://journal-law.com/>

journallaw1@yahoo.co

Chief in Editor Prof. SUHAIL H. AL-FATLAW

General Supervisor-Prof. TALAL ALNADAW

Secretary of the Editorial Board-Prof. SALEH AL-TAI

Editorial Board

- 1- Prof. HOSSAM GHARABAWI: University of Baghdad – Iraq
- 2- Prof. ADEL AL ALI -University of Al - Isra University- Jordan.
- 3- Prof. YURIY PYVOVAR. Department of Constitutional and Administrative Law -National Aviation University, Ukraine.
- 4- Prof. JAMIL MUSAB-University of Baghdad – Iraq.
- 5- Prof. E SAHIB OBEID AL – FATAWI-Amman National University – Jordan.
- 6- Prof. MUSLEH HASSAN AL – HADITHI-Al-Rashid University, Iraq.
- 7- Dr. Nguyen Binh An (B. An Nguyen) Law Faculty, Binh Duong University- Vietnam
- 8- Prof. AAD ALI AL-KAISSI -University of Sharjah-UAE.
- 9-PROF. ASHJAN AL-ZUHAIRY
Al-Qasim University, College of Sharia and Islamic Studies- Saudi Arabia-Systems Department
- 10-- Prof. ACHOUR FTIMA -Dean of the Faculty of Law – Algeria.
- 11- Dr. OROOBA JABAR ABDEL HUSSEIN,
DIRECTOR of the Journal's Department

ADVISERS

Prof. Noman Al-Khatib, President of the University of Jordan

Pro. Shafiq al-Samarrai - University President-Belgium

Prof. Emad Rabee Vice President of Jerash University-Jordan

Prof. Ahmed Abu Shanab - Amman Arab University- Jordan

Prof. Mohammed Wsal- Dean of the Faculty of Law-Syria

Prof. Ali Al_husenawe- Dean of the Faculty of Law-Iraq

Prof. Mohamed Hossam- Dean of the Faculty of Law-Oman

**Prof. Ahmed Hawamdeh- Dean of the Faculty of Law- Jerash University
- Jordan**

Dr. Abderrahman Alarman -Dean of the Law Faculty-Jordan

Prof. Mohamed Aboul Ela- Academy-Egypt

Prof. Asaid Mostafa Aboalker-Academy-Egypt

Prof. Khalil Elias Murad -Denmark

Prof. Dr. Mustafa Eчек- Academy-Turkey

Prof. Ahmed Fedaioglu Academy-Turkey

Prof. Karim Harzallah- Academy- Algeria

Prof. Aiser Khalil Al-Obidi- Baghdad university Iraq

**Prof. Amrouche elhoucine Faculty of Law and Political Science -Yahiya
Fares University-Medea –Algeria**

Dr. Murtada Abdullah Khairi- Academy-Sudan

Rosi Topham- Academy-UK

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

P.ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

IMPACT FACTOR 2.329

VOL. 45-2-ISSUE 3-June 2025 -Special issue

First edition 2011

The Journal certified by:

 ESCI	
<p>The Journal of Law and Political Sciences is published by the Law and Political Research Center which is accredited by CVR - Det Centrale Virksomhedsregister-Denmark</p>	 cvr virk
<p>Accredited by the Faculty of Law - Aalborg Academy of Sciences –Denmark</p>	
<p>Islamic Word Science citation Center</p>	
<p>INTERNATIONAL Scientific Indexing</p>	<p>QUALITY IMPACT VALUE 2.329</p>
<p>TOGETHER WE REACH THE GOAL</p>	<p>QUALITY IMPACT VALUE 7.234</p>

Published Terms in the journal:

1. Number of pages of no more than 40 pages. 14 × 21 cm;
2. Subject of research in the Law and political and Islamic law;
3. Researcher must use scientific sources, or documents depends referred to in accordance with the scientific bases used in scientific research;
4. The research includes an abstract of no more than 150 words.
5. The research includes keyword.
6. The introduction shall include the importance of research and the research problem. The introduction shall not exceed two pages.
7. The research referred on two experts, to ensure compliance with the terms of the researcher scientific research;
8. Written in the footnote in the bottom of the page and printed electronically.
9. The researcher shall have a PhD in law, or political science or Islamic law.
10. Research written in English, French or Arabic language.
11. The researcher is responsible for the views expressed in his research.
12. Research is sent by e-mail to the head of the editorial board.
13. At the end of the research conclusion includes the pleadings and recommendations.
14. List of sources by alphabet at the end of research.
15. The research may not be published in another journal, or in a book.

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

P.ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

IMPACT FACTOR 2.329

VOL. 45-2-ISSUE 3-June 2025 -Special issue

First edition 2011

International Journal Evaluation

<p>Clarivate Analytics WEB OF SCIENCE™</p>	<p>Clarivate Analytics EMERGING SOURCES CITATION INDEX</p>	<p>Clarivate Analytics WEB OF SCIENCE</p>	<p>AALBORG ACADEMY OF SCIENCE</p>
<p>EBSCO HOST</p>	<p>ExLibris Part of Clarivate</p>	<p>Web of Science Group</p>	<p>INDEX COPERNICUS INTERNATIONAL</p>
<p>International Innovative Journal Impact Factor (IIJIF)</p>	<p>International Society of Universal Research in Sciences</p>	<p>JIF JIFACTOR</p>	<p>WBR UK</p>
<p>EcoLink</p>	<p>INNO SPACE SJI Scientific Journal Impact Factor</p>	<p>ExLibris a ProQuest Company</p>	<p>CuteStat.com website stats and valuation</p>
<p>Crossref</p>	<p>DRJI</p>	<p>ISC</p>	<p>SSRN</p>

INTERNATIONAL
 Scientific Indexing
 Fresh Ideas for Growing your Citations

Certificate

This is to certify that **Journal of Law and Political Science** is indexed in International Scientific Indexing (ISI). The Journal has Impact Factor Value of **2.329** based on International Citation Report (ICR) for the year **2022-2023**. The URL for journal on our server is <https://isindexing.com/isi/journaldetails.php?id=4032>

Editor ICR Team (ISD)

 International Scientific Indexing (ISI)

Contents of Vol. No. (46/2) of issue July-2025

1. **A Comparative Analysis of Parliamentary Roles in Public Administration.** By VALENTYNA GOSHOVSKA and others. p. 10.
2. **Balancing State Discretion and the Rule of Law: Challenges, Opportunities, and Prospects in the Era.** By VLADYSLAV NOVITSKYI. and others, p. 35.
3. **The Right to Peace as a Fundamental Human Need: The Case for Global Consolidation.** By NATALIYA ONISHCHENKO and others, p. 56.
4. **The Peculiarities of Inter-Institutional Interaction of Transregional Cooperation Legal Regulation: Trends in the Contemporary EU.** By VIKTOR SHCHERBAK and others, p. 80.
5. **Vital Security Paradigm in the New Millennium: Coordinate System and State-of-the-Art.** By IGOR RYZHOV and others. p. 94.
6. **Providing Psychological Assistance to Police Forces in Wartime: The Ukrainian Experience.** By OLENA FEDORENKO and others. p. 122.
7. **The Study of Military Conflict: Human Existence in Times of Distress,** by OLGA RUDENKO. and others. p.146.
8. **Legal Framework for the Professional Selection of Forensic Experts to Ensure Impartial Judgements.** By ROMAN KIRIN. and others. p. 161.
9. **Analyzing the Significance of the Hague Tribunal and International Legal Institutions in Cases Related to the Armed Conflict in Ukraine.** by OLEKSANDR LYSAK, and others. p. 180.
10. **Ukrainian State Border Control: Legislative Support for the Prevention of Violations.** By YAROSLAV KUSHNIR. P. 201.
11. **Formation of the Judicial System in Accordance with the Institution of Human Rights.** LIDIYA MOSKVYCH. and others. p. 218.
12. **Long-term Thinking in Public Governance under the Digital Era.** By IRYNA PIATNYCHUK. and others. p. 246.
13. **NATO as a Collective Security Organization in the EU after the Outbreak of War in Ukraine.** by OLHA DZHYHORA and others. p. 255.
14. **Management Approaches to Ensuring National Security: Legal and Organizational Challenges.** By VIKTORIYA SYDORENKO. and others. p. 272.
15. **Legal Aspects of Penalties for Public Asset Misuse: Challenges of Law Enforcement studying.** By IGOR PARYZKYI. and others. p. 299.
16. **The Ukraine War and the World Balance of Power: The Perspectives of a Multipolar World.** By VASYL VERESHCHAK and others. p. 323.

(15)

**LEGAL ASPECTS OF PENALTIES FOR PUBLIC
ASSET MISUSE: CHALLENGES OF LAW
ENFORCEMENTSTUDYING**

Receipt 21May

Approval 30 June

Publishing July 2025

IGOR PARYZKYI

Candidate of Legal Sciences, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor, Department of Marketing, Economics, Management and Administration, Pro-rector, National Academy of Management, Kyiv, Ukraine. i.paryzkyi@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6835-5930>

MAKSYM CHERNENOK

Candidate of Law, Associate Professor, Department of Law Enforcement and General Legal Disciplines, Faculty of Law, Chernihiv Polytechnic National University, Chernihiv, Ukraine. maksche1204@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-6080-8805>

VOLODYMYR ORTYNSKYI

Doctor of Law, Honored Lawyer of Ukraine, Professor, Director of the Educational and Research Institute of Law, Psychology and Innovative Education, Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine- volodymyr.l.ortynskyi@lpnu.ua
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9041-6330>

OLEKSII HUMIN

Doctor of Law, Professor, Head of the Department of International and Criminal Law, Educational and Research Institute of Law, Psychology and Innovative Education, Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine. oleksii.m.humin@lpnu.ua
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8016-945X>

NATALIYA ORTYNSKA

Doctor of Law, Professor, Department of Theory of Law and Constitutionalism, Educational and Research Institute of Law, Psychology and Innovative Education, Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine- natalius2008@ukr.net
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5061-5340>

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to examine the problems of criminal liability for misuse of public resources; the object is criminal law provisions and the practice of their application in Ukraine and the EU. The study reveals key shortcomings of the

current legislation of Ukraine, in particular, the lack of a mechanism for bringing legal entities to criminal liability and the unclear criteria for distinguishing crimes from administrative offenses. A comparative analysis of international experience has shown that the EU countries and the USA widely use a combination of criminal law and preventive instruments to prevent such offenses. The author substantiates the expediency of introducing a unified register of financial violations and compliance systems in the public sector in Ukraine. The practical significance of the results is that they can be used to prepare legislative initiatives and improve the practice of investigative and prosecutorial authorities.

Keywords: *criminal liability, state resources, misuse, law enforcement practice, international experience, corporate responsibility, financial control, anti-corruption mechanisms, legal harmonization, compliance*

1- INTRODUCTION

The problem of misuse of public resources is becoming increasingly acute on a global scale, as misuse of budget funds and other state assets undermines economic security, public confidence in the authorities, and the country's international reputation. For Ukraine, this problem is particularly relevant in the context of ongoing challenges related to public sector reforms, the fight against corruption, and the need for transparent management of financial flows. Violations related to the misappropriation of public resources not only cause material damage but also create systemic risks associated with ineffective management decisions and the devaluation of the rule of law. In the current scientific literature, the problem of combating the abuse of public resources is receiving a lot of attention both in Ukraine and in the countries of the European Union and the world. In particular, Allegrezza and Bruzzese¹ emphasize the importance of strengthening control and supervision mechanisms in the EU finance sector, while Souto² emphasizes the importance of criminal liability of legal entities for financial crimes. A number of works³ demonstrate the national law enforcement practice of Ukraine, focusing on the problems of proving intent and proving abuse. At

¹ Allegrezza, S., & Bruzzese, G. (2025). Supervision and enforcement of EU's anti-money-laundering and countering the financing of terrorism. In R. D'Ambrosio, et al. (Eds.), *EU banking and capital markets regulation* (pp. 487–521). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70529-8_14

² Souto, M. A. (2022). Money laundering, cybercrime and criminal responsibility of legal persons. In Y. Liu, et al. (Eds.), *Cybercrimes and financial crimes in the global era* (pp. 145–164). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-3189-5_16

³ Kuzmenko, O., Koval, S., & Koval, V. (2021). Criminal liability of legal entities for environmental crimes: Problems of law enforcement practice. *Cuestiones Políticas*, 39(70), 621–636. <https://doi.org/10.46398/cuestpol.3970.52>

the same time, the studies by Makarenko et al.⁴ and Borovyk⁵ consider related aspects of combating natural resource crime and corruption. Despite the existing scientific developments, there is still no comprehensive analytical model that would combine international experience and Ukrainian practice, in particular with regard to the liability of legal entities, interagency coordination, and the use of digital control tools. The issues of distinguishing between criminal offenses and administrative violations, the lack of mechanisms for criminal liability of legal entities in Ukraine, and the problems of effective interaction between investigative bodies and financial control bodies remain gaps. Comparative analysis of international and national practices is mostly limited to a descriptive level without a deep systemic generalization and proposals for harmonization of legislation.

In view of this, the purpose of this paper is to study the problems of criminalization of misuse of public resources in Ukraine, analyze international experience and practice of the European Union in this area, identify gaps in law enforcement practice, characterize the main obstacles to effective legal response, and develop practical proposals for improving the criminal legislation of Ukraine in line with current international trends.

Literature review

The issue of criminal liability for violations in the use of public resources is the subject of active research in both foreign and Ukrainian scientific literature. The study by Allegrezza and Bruzzese⁶ focuses on the system of supervision and enforcement of anti-corruption norms in the EU, which is an important example for improving the national control system. At the same time, Foti and Malino⁷ demonstrate the impact of digital technologies and artificial intelligence on areas related to financial transparency and control. The study by Al-Kayid et al.⁸ reveals the relationship between digital

⁴ Makarenko, O. Y., Makarenko, N. A., Nazymko, O. V., Hromenko, Y. O., & Nesterenko, K. O. (2021). Problematic issues of criminal prosecution for the illegal extraction of mineral resources. *Scientific Bulletin of National Mining University*, 2021(4), 139–145. <https://doi.org/10.33271/nvngu/2021-4/139>

⁵ Borovyk, A. V. (2020). European standards of criminal liability for corruption offenses and their prevention. *Actual Problems of State and Law*, 85, 5–12. <https://doi.org/10.32837/apdp.v0i85.1820>

⁶ Allegrezza, S., & Bruzzese, G. (2025). *Id.*

⁷ Foti, D., & Malino, E. (2024). Third Parties in Italian Criminal Proceedings. In S. Ruggeri, et al. (Eds), *Third Parties in Criminal Proceedings. Legal Studies in International, European and Comparative Criminal Law, Vol 10*. Springer, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-73970-5>

⁸ Al-Kayid, J. H., El-Manaseer, S. A., Al Khawatreh, A. M., & Ibra-him, A. A. (2023). Reflections on the impact of digital transformation on criminal policy. In E. A. ElTayeb, et al. (Eds.), *Artificial intelligence (AI) and finance* (pp. 120–133). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-39158-3_11

transformation and changes in criminal policy, while Lanz and Mijic⁹ draw attention to the risks of legal liability in the context of the use of artificial intelligence. Klein et al.¹⁰ explore practical approaches to combating new types of financial crimes, in particular in the field of cryptocurrencies. Rembert et al.¹¹ examine aspects of the liability of public officials, which is also relevant to violations in the use of public resources. Nikolinakos¹² analyzes the adaptation of European legislation to the digital age, emphasizing the relevance of reforms in the legal sphere. Souto¹³ examines the criminal liability of legal entities for financial crimes, which is especially important given the current challenges in Ukraine.

Giannini and Kwik¹⁴ provide a comparative analysis of the regulation of liability for negligence in the field of artificial intelligence and autonomous systems, which can be extrapolated to public administration. Pekarchuk and Chaika¹⁵ consider the protection of state symbols and their legal protection, while Movchan et al.¹⁶ explore models of combating smuggling and illegal movement of goods, demonstrating examples of legislative reform. The issue of mining without proper permits is analyzed by Makarenko et al.¹⁷, which is related to the topic of protecting public resources. Lee¹⁸

⁹ Lanz, M., & Mijic, S. (2023). Risks associated with the use of natural language generation: Swiss civil liability law perspective. In E. Schweighofer, et al. (Eds.), *Multidisciplinary perspectives on artificial intelligence and the law* (pp. 297–314). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-41264-6_17

¹⁰ Klein, G., Assadi, D., & Zwillig, M. (2024). Fighting fire with fire: Combating criminal abuse of cryptocurrency with a P2P mindset. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 26(4), 123–145. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-024-10498-7>

¹¹ Rembert, D. A., Joseph, J. J., Threadcraft-Walker, W., Thread-craft, M., Brown, D., Soyele, O. E., & Henderson, H. (2023). Criminal liability for correctional officer excessive use of force. *Crime, Law and Social Change*, 79(2), 105–128. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10611-022-10036-z>

¹² Nikolinakos, N. Th. (2024). Adapting EU liability rules to the digital age and artificial intelligence: The European Commission's 2021 inception impact assessment. In *Adapting the EU civil liability regime to the digital age: Artificial intelligence, robotics, and other emerging technologies* (pp. 253–326). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-67969-8_6

¹³ Souto, M. A. (2022). *Id.*

¹⁴ Giannini, A., & Kwik, J. (2023). Negligence failures and negligence fixes: A comparative analysis of criminal regulation of AI and autonomous vehicles. *Criminal Law Forum*, 34(1), 43–85. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10609-023-09451-1>

¹⁵ Pekarchuk, V. M., & Chaika, V. Yu. (2020). Problems of legal liability for infringement on state symbols. *South Ukrainian Law Journal*, 3(1), 103–115. <https://doi.org/10.32755/sjcriminal.2020.01.103>

¹⁶ Movchan, R. O., Dudorov, O. O., Vozniuk, A. A., Areshonkov, V. Yu., & Lutsenko, Yu. V. (2021). Combating commodity smuggling in Ukraine: In search of the optimal legislative model. *Amazonia Investiga*, 10(47), 142–151. <https://doi.org/10.34069/AI/2021.47.11.14>

¹⁷ Makarenko, O. Y., Makarenko, N. A., Nazymko, O. V., Hromenko, Y. O., & Nesterenko, K. O. (2021). *Id.*

examines examples of misuse of university funds, showing the mechanisms of bringing to justice in a specific case. Kuzmenko et al.¹⁹ focuses on environmental crimes and liability of legal entities, demonstrating the importance of an expanded approach to criminal liability. Demchuk and Lenger²⁰ emphasize the interconnection of administrative and criminal liability in the field of ecology.

Basic approaches to the differentiation of criminal liability are outlined in Antoniuk²¹, and the use of electronic information resources in public administration is discussed in detail by Blinova²². Khalizov²³ analyzes administrative liability for violations of land legislation, which can be the basis for strengthening criminal liability in related areas. Finally, Borovyk²⁴ examines the European standards of criminal liability for corruption offenses, which is the basis for the implementation of similar approaches in Ukrainian legislation. Particularly noteworthy is the study by Movchan et al.²⁵, which not only demonstrates the problems of smuggling but also emphasizes the need to find an optimal model of legislative regulation of economic crimes. The work of Makarenko et al.²⁶ reveals the complexities of criminal prosecution for illegal extraction of natural resources, which is a form of misuse of state property. Pekarchuk and Chaika²⁷ place an important emphasis on the imperfection of criminal law in terms of protecting state symbols and protecting the interests of the state, demonstrating the need for further harmonization of legal norms.

¹⁸ Lee, J. M. (2013). Criminal liability for misappropriation of university-industry cooperation funds: Supreme Court decision 2009Do13751 rendered on October 13, 2011. *Journal of Law and Politics Research*, 13(2), 123–145. https://www.kci.go.kr/kciportal/landing/article.kci?arti_id=ART001790863

¹⁹ Kuzmenko, O., Koval, S., & Koval, V. (2021). *Id.*

²⁰ Demchuk, A. M., & Lenger, Y. I. (2024). Administrative and criminal liability for environmental offenses in the field of land relations. *New Ukrainian Law*, 5, 67–73. <https://doi.org/10.51989/NUL.2024.5.8>

²¹ Antoniuk, N. O. (2020). Means of differentiation of criminal liability. *Law of Ukraine*, 2020(2), 228–245. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340097968_Zasobi_diferenciacii_kriminalnoi_vidpovidalnosti

²² Blinova, H. O. (2021). Legal foundations for the use of electronic information resources in the concept of a digital state. *Problems of Modern Transformations. Series: Law, Public Governance and Administration*, 2, 53–60. <https://doi.org/10.54929/pmtl-issue2-2021-10>

²³ Khalizov, D. V. (2024). On the issue of administrative liability for violations of legislation in the field of land use by farms. *Bulletin of the Criminological Association of Ukraine*, 2(32), 896–903. <https://doi.org/10.32631/vca.2024.2.69>

²⁴ Borovyk, A. V. (2020). *Id.*

²⁵ Movchan, R. O., Dudorov, O. O., Vozniuk, A. A., Areshonkov, V. Yu., & Lutsenko, Yu. V. (2021). *Id.*

²⁶ Makarenko, O. Y., Makarenko, N. A., Nazymko, O. V., Hromenko, Y. O., & Nesterenko, K. O. (2021). *Id.*

²⁷ Pekarchuk, V. M., & Chaika, V. Yu. (2020). *Id.*

Lee¹⁸ examines the case law on theft of university funds in South Korea, which is an illustrative example of how to respond to the misuse of state or public resources in the field of education. Kuzmenko et al.²⁸ analyze the criminal liability of legal entities for environmental crimes, which can be transferred to other areas of public resource protection. Demchuk and Lenger²⁹ focus on the interconnection of administrative and criminal liability in the field of land use, which is important in the context of law enforcement practice in relation to state assets. Blinova³⁰ examines the legal basis for the use of electronic information resources in public administration, which raises the issue of digital transparency in the use of public resources. Khalizov³¹ draws attention to the problems of administrative liability in the field of land relations, which often accompany crimes of embezzlement of public assets. Borovyk's³² analytical review demonstrates the European standards of criminal liability for corruption offenses, which is the basis for the implementation of such instruments in the national legislation of Ukraine.

Despite the wide coverage of the topic in the scientific literature, a number of issues remain unresolved. In particular, there is still no unified approach to criminal liability of legal entities and no clear criteria for distinguishing a crime from an administrative offense in the field of public resources.

Research methods

The research was conducted as part of the study of Ukrainian law enforcement practice and international experience in combating crimes in the field of public resources. The analysis was based on a systematic study of the provisions of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, court practice, official reports of the NABU, the SIB and the Office of the Prosecutor General of Ukraine. In addition, reports from the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF), the European Public Prosecutor's Office (EPPO), the U.S. Department of Justice and the U.S. Office of the Inspector General were used. The main research methods used were the formal logical method, comparative legal analysis, the method of systematization and generalization of scientific sources, and content analysis of judicial and statistical information. In addition, graphical data visualization was used to display key indicators of international statistics. The study was conducted using open data and official publications of scientists available in international scientometric databases and on the websites of official institutions.

²⁸⁾ Kuzmenko, O., Koval, S., & Koval, V. (2021). *Id.*

²⁹⁾ Demchuk, A. M., & Lenger, Y. I. (2024). *Id.*

³⁰⁾ Blinova, H. O. (2021). *Id.*

³¹⁾ Khalizov, D. V. (2024). *Id.*

³²⁾ Borovyk, A. V. (2020). *Id.*

2. RESEARCH RESULTS

2.1. THEORETICAL AND LEGISLATIVE FOUNDATIONS OF LIABILITY FOR PUBLIC ASSET MISUSE

In modern criminal law doctrine, the misuse of state resources is considered as a set of acts related to the unlawful disposal, expenditure, redistribution or other use of material, financial and information resources belonging to the state or created with its participation. Theoretical approaches focus on the characteristics of the object of the crime – state resources, which include budget funds, state property, rights to information and other assets intended for the performance of state functions. The basis of illegality is the absence of legal grounds for such use or violation of the purpose, purpose and procedure for using resources defined by law³³. Considerable attention is paid to the characteristics of the subject of the crime, as the theory emphasizes that the misuse of public resources is usually committed by persons who have certain powers to dispose of these resources or have access to them through their official position. In this context, it is important to distinguish between the abuse of power and official position and the actual misuse of public resources, which has an independent object and subject of encroachment³⁴. At the same time, scholars emphasize that state resources are not only material assets, but also information, the rights to which belong to the state, and its unauthorized use should also be covered by criminal law protection³⁵.

In addition, theorists emphasize the importance of taking into account the nature and degree of social danger of such acts. In particular, the misuse of public resources is considered a crime with a high degree of public danger because it violates the principles of public administration and undermines trust in public institutions³⁶. At the same time, some scientific approaches note that special attention should be paid to justifying the differentiation of criminal liability depending on the consequences, the amount of misused resources and the motives for committing the crime³⁷.

An important area of theoretical research is the idea of harmonizing the national approach with European standards, where the misuse of public resources is defined as any intentional or reckless use of state resources contrary to applicable law, goals or obligations under public law. In particular, Allegrezza and Bruzzese³⁸, in the context of European law, point out the importance of comprehensive control over the use of public funds and the need for strict liability for their misuse or illegal use. This indicates a tendency towards an expanded understanding of illegality, which includes not only a

³³ Pekarchuk, V. M., & Chaika, V. Yu. (2020). *Id.*

³⁴ Makarenko, O. Y., Makarenko, N. A., Nazymko, O. V., Hromenko, Y. O., & Nesterenko, K. O. (2021). *Id.*

³⁵ Blinova, H. O. (2021). *Id.*

³⁶ Borovyk, A. V. (2020). *Id.*

³⁷ Antoniuk, N. O. (2020). *Id.*

³⁸ Allegrezza, S., & Bruzzese, G. (2025). *Id.*

clear violation of the law, but also any actions contrary to the public interest and the principles of good governance.

The analysis of the current legislation of Ukraine shows that the issue of criminal liability for the misuse of public resources is regulated by a number of provisions of the Criminal Code of Ukraine (hereinafter – the CCU). In particular, these articles include Article 191 “Misappropriation, embezzlement or seizure of property through abuse of office”, Article 210 “Misuse of budget funds”, Article 364 “Abuse of power or position” and others. The legislation emphasizes the necessity of intent and direct violation of the procedure for the use of budgetary or state resources. It is also worth noting that law enforcement practice points to problems in proving the targeted nature of funds and confirming the fact of abuse of power³⁹.

At the international level, standards for combating violations in the field of public resources are shaped by the United Nations⁴⁰, the Council of Europe Convention on Criminal Law⁴¹ and the norms of the European Union. The EU has a zero-tolerance principle for the abuse of public finances, which is reflected in Regulation 883/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the investigation of fraud and abuse prejudicial to the financial interests of the EU⁴². International doctrine also widely covers the problems of legal entities’ liability and the introduction of internal control systems⁴³.

Particular attention in the modern legal field is paid to the comparative legal analysis of the approaches of the EU, the USA and Ukraine to the criminalization of violations in the field of public resources. These approaches are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparative Legal Analysis of the Criminal Law Regulation of Liability for Violations in the Field of Use of State Resources

Country/ Region	Regulatory framework	The main elements of the crime	Features of liability
Ukraine	Criminal Code of Ukraine (Art. 191,	Intentional misuse of state resources;	Liability is triggered by intent, significant

³⁹ Movchan, R. O., Dudorov, O. O., Vozniuk, A. A., Areshonkov, V. Yu., & Lutsenko, Yu. V. (2021). *Id.*

⁴⁰ United Nations. (2003). *United Nations Convention against Corruption*. <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/corruption/uncac.html>

⁴¹ Council of Europe. (1999). *Criminal Law Convention on Corruption* (ETS No. 173). <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list?module=treaty-detail&treatynum=173>

⁴² United Nations. (2003). *Id.*

⁴³ Souto, M. A. (2022). *Id.*

	Art. 210, Art. 364, etc.) ⁴⁴	abuse of office; violation of budget discipline	damage or grave consequences
European Union	EU Regulation 883/2013, Council of Europe Convention on Criminal Law on Corruption ⁴⁵	Misuse of public funds, fraud with budgetary funds, corruption	Includes liability of legal entities and administrative control instruments
USA	Fraud Enforcement and Recovery Act, US Criminal Code ⁴⁶	Falsification of documents, misuse of budgetary resources, violation of public procurement rules	High fines, imprisonment and long-term suspension from public service

Source: Created by the author on the basis of Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine⁴⁷, Allegrezza and Bruzzese⁴⁸, Movchan et al.⁴⁹, Souto⁵⁰, United Nations⁵¹, Council of Europe⁵², European Parliament & Council of the European Union⁵³, U.S. Congress⁵⁴.

⁴⁴ Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. (2001). *Criminal Code of Ukraine* No. 2341-III of April 5 2021 (as amended). <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2341-14#Text>

⁴⁵ Council of Europe. (1999). *Id.*

⁴⁶ U.S. Congress. (2009). *Fraud Enforcement and Recovery Act of 2009, Public Law 111–21* <https://www.congress.gov/111/plaws/publ21/PLAW-111publ21.pdf>

⁴⁷ Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. (2001). *Id.*

⁴⁸ Allegrezza, S., & Bruzzese, G. (2025). *Id.*

⁴⁹ Movchan, R. O., Dudorov, O. O., Vozniuk, A. A., Areshonkov, V. Yu., & Lutsenko, Yu. V. (2021). *Id.*

⁵⁰ Souto, M. A. (2022). *Id.*

⁵¹ United Nations. (2003). *United Nations Convention against Corruption*. <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/corruption/uncac.html>

⁵² Council of Europe. (1999). *Id.*

⁵³ European Parliament & Council of the European Union. (2013). Regulation (EU) No 883/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 September 2013 concerning investigations conducted by the European Anti-Fraud Office¹ (OLAF). *Official Journal of the European Union*, L248, 1–22. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32013R0883>

⁵⁴ U.S. Congress. (2009). *Id.*

Thus, the study shows that Ukrainian legislation in this area needs to be harmonized with international standards and a clear delineation of *corpus delicti* by the criteria of object, subject and subjective party. International approaches focus on prevention, increased responsibility of officials and control over the actions of legal entities, which should also be taken into account in further reform of the national legal system.

2.2. LAW ENFORCEMENT PRACTICE AND KEY PROBLEMS IN UKRAINE

One of the key problems in the area of criminal liability for misuse of public resources is the difficulty of proving the fact of intent and establishing a causal link between the actions of a person and the damage caused. Often, during the investigation and trial, there are difficulties with the evidence base to confirm the targeted nature of the use of funds, especially in cases of their distribution through complex budget programs or multi-level public procurement mechanisms⁵⁵. In addition, the problem of qualifying acts remains unresolved, when the line between violation of financial discipline and a crime is blurred, and law enforcement officers face conflicts and conflicting interpretations of the law⁵⁶.

A separate issue is the lack of proper practice of bringing legal entities to criminal liability, although such opportunities are provided for by both international standards⁵⁷ and modern approaches to corporate criminal liability⁵⁸. Existing enforcement problems are also related to the ineffectiveness of internal financial control in government agencies and imperfect interaction between investigative and audit bodies. An analysis of court practice shows that some criminal proceedings are completed without convictions due to insufficient evidence or formal violations during the investigation⁵⁹. Table 2 summarizes the main problems of law enforcement in the area of criminal liability for the misuse of public resources.

Table 2. The main problems of law enforcement in the field of criminal prosecution for misuse of public resources

Problem	The essence of the problem	Example or consequence in law
---------	----------------------------	-------------------------------

⁵⁵ Movchan, R. O., Dudorov, O. O., Vozniuk, A. A., Areshonkov, V. Yu., & Lutsenko, Yu. V. (2021). *Id.*

⁵⁶ Makarenko, O. Y., Makarenko, N. A., Nazymko, O. V., Hromenko, Y. O., & Nesterenko, K. O. (2021). *Id.*

⁵⁷ Souto, M. A. (2022). *Id.*

⁵⁸ Allegrezza, S., & Bruzzese, G. (2025). *Id.*

⁵⁹ Kuzmenko, O., Koval, S., & Koval, V. (2021). *Id.*

		enforcement practice
Difficulties in proving intent and causation	Lack of clear evidence of intentional violation of the intended use of public funds	Closure of criminal proceedings due to lack of sufficient evidence
Blurring the line between a crime and a disciplinary offense	Lack of legal criteria for a clear distinction	Incorrect qualification of actions or dismissal of criminal charges
Weak mechanism of liability of legal entities	Lack of effective legal mechanisms for bringing corporations to criminal liability	Violations committed in the interests of legal entities remain unaddressed
Imperfect interaction between investigation and audit	Insufficient coordination between regulatory and law enforcement agencies	Delayed investigations and formal closure of cases
Formal violations during the pre-trial investigation	Failure to comply with procedural rules and violation of suspects' rights	Reversal of court decisions or inadmissibility of evidence

Source: Created by the author on the basis of Movchan et al.⁶⁰, Makarenko et al.⁶¹, Souto⁶², Allegrezza and Bruzzese⁶³, Kuzmenko et al.⁶⁴

⁶⁰ Movchan, R. O., Dudorov, O. O., Vozniuk, A. A., Areshonkov, V. Yu., & Lutsenko, Yu. V. (2021). *Id.*

⁶¹ Makarenko, O. Y., Makarenko, N. A., Nazymko, O. V., Hromenko, Y. O., & Nesterenko, K. O. (2021). *Id.*

Thus, the analysis of the identified problems indicates the need for a systematic review of approaches to law enforcement practice in this area, in particular by legislating clear criteria for distinguishing between a crime and an administrative offense, improving procedural rules and intensifying work on the implementation of international standards of criminal liability of legal entities.

2.3. COMPARATIVE INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND DIRECTIONS FOR REFORM

The generalization of foreign experience and the practice of the European Union shows that the issue of combating crimes in the use of public resources is a key element of the integrity policy and good public finance management. The EU and leading countries of the world have a comprehensive approach that combines criminal law mechanisms, administrative control, corporate responsibility and preventive measures. The European Union pays special attention to building independent anti-corruption bodies and ensuring transparency of financial flows⁶⁵. An important tool is the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF), which is authorized to investigate abuses that harm the EU's financial interests and to cooperate with law enforcement agencies of member states⁶⁶.

In the United States, the effective fight against the misuse of public funds is based on strict legislation, a system of independent financial inspections and a well-established system of control over public procurement⁶⁷. The American model envisages not only criminal liability of individuals, but also significant attention to corporate liability, which allows legal entities to be held accountable for violations in the field of public resources⁶⁸.

Among the key elements of foreign practice is the introduction of a compliance system in the public sector, when organizations are required to implement internal policies to detect, prevent and respond to abuse. A number of countries require regular financial reporting and auditing by independent auditors, the results of which are published for public access. Practice shows that such openness helps to increase public trust in the authorities and minimizes corruption risks⁶⁹. Table 3 systematizes the main elements of international experience and practice of the European Union in combating crimes in the field of public resources.

⁶² Souto, M. A. (2022). *Id.*

⁶³ Allegrezza, S., & Bruzzese, G. (2025). *Id.*

⁶⁴ Kuzmenko, O., Koval, S., & Koval, V. (2021). *Id.*

⁶⁵ Allegrezza, S., & Bruzzese, G. (2025). *Id.*

⁶⁶ European Parliament & Council of the European Union. (2013). *Id.*

⁶⁷ U.S. Congress. (2009). *Id.*

⁶⁸ Souto, M. A. (2022). *Id.*

⁶⁹ Borovyk, A. V. (2020). *Id.*

Table 3. The main elements of international practice of combating crimes in the field of public resources

Country /region	Institutional mechanisms	Main approaches to counteracting	Peculiarities of criminal regulation of law
European Union	OLAF, European Public Prosecution Office (EPPO)	Independent investigations, transparency of public finances, harmonization of legal norms	Uniform standards and the possibility of holding legal entities liable
USA	Ministry of Justice, Inspectorates of Auditors General, Public Procurement Commission	Strict financial audit, procurement control, compliance system	Harsh sanctions, the possibility of plea bargaining and fines for corporations
Great Britain	National Audit Office, Serious Fraud Office	Regular public audit, detection and investigation of crimes in the public sector	Liability of legal entities and officials based on the results of independent investigations

Source: Created by the author on the basis of Allegrezza and Bruzzese⁷⁰, European Parliament & Council of the European Union⁷¹, Souto⁷², Borovyk⁷³, U.S. Congress⁷⁴

Foreign experience shows that effective counteraction to crimes in the field of public resources is possible only with a comprehensive approach that combines criminal law measures, preventive mechanisms, a developed system of financial control and a high level of transparency in public administration. These approaches deserve to be

⁷⁰ Allegrezza, S., & Bruzzese, G. (2025). *Id.*

⁷¹ European Parliament & Council of the European Union. (2013). *Id.*

⁷² Souto, M. A. (2022). *Id.*

⁷³ Borovyk, A. V. (2020). *Id.*

⁷⁴ U.S. Congress. (2009). *Id.*

taken into account when reforming the national system of combating violations in the field of public resources in Ukraine.

For a better understanding of the scale and effectiveness of combating crimes in the field of public resources in different countries, we present comparative statistics on the number of cases opened, the average amount of damage and the percentage of cases brought to a guilty verdict.

The methodological basis of the study was the use of official reports of international and national anti-fraud and corruption bodies. Data was collected by analyzing the annual publications of the European Anti-Fraud Office⁷⁵ and the annual reports of the European Public Prosecutor's Office⁷⁶. Data on the situation in the United States were based on publications of the U.S. Department of Justice⁷⁷ and reports of the U.S. Office of Inspector General⁷⁸. Information on the state of law enforcement in Ukraine was summarized on the basis of annual reports of the National Anti-Corruption Bureau of Ukraine (NABU)⁷⁹, the State Bureau of Investigation of Ukraine (SBI)⁸⁰, and statistical reports of the Office of the Prosecutor General of Ukraine (OGPU)⁸¹.

Quantitative indicators were standardized and brought to a single format for comparison. The average amount of damages was calculated based on the average values for the reporting periods. The share of cases brought to a guilty verdict was determined by the ratio of the number of guilty verdicts to the total number of cases initiated according to official reporting data. Currency figures are converted into euros or US dollars at the average official exchange rate for the reporting period. To visualize the number of opened criminal cases on misuse of public resources and the effectiveness of completing investigations in the form of guilty verdicts, a diagram was created (Figure 1).

⁷⁵ European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF). (2024). OLAF report 2023: Protecting the EU's financial interests. *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://ec.europa.eu/anti-fraud>

⁷⁶ European Public Prosecutor's Office (EPPO). (2024). Annual report 2023. *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://www.eppo.europa.eu>

⁷⁷ U.S. Department of Justice. (2023). *Annual report on fraud and misuse of public funds*. <https://www.justice.gov>

⁷⁸ U.S. Office of Inspector General. (2023). *Semiannual report to Congress*. <https://www.oig.gov>

⁷⁹ National Anti-Corruption Bureau of Ukraine (NABU). (2023). *Annual report*. <https://nabu.gov.ua>

⁸⁰ State Bureau of Investigation of Ukraine (SBI). (2023). *Annual report*. <https://dbr.gov.ua>

⁸¹ Office of the Prosecutor General of Ukraine (OGPU). (2023). *Annual statistical report*. <https://gp.gov.ua>

Figure 1. Dynamics of opened criminal cases and the share of cases brought to a guilty verdict in the EU, the USA, the UK and Ukraine (2023)

Source: Created by the author on the basis of European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF)⁸², European Public Prosecutor's Office (EPPO)⁸³, U.S. Department of Justice⁸⁴, U.S. Office of Inspector General⁸⁵, National Anti-Corruption Bureau of Ukraine (NABU)⁸⁶, State Bureau of Investigation of Ukraine (SBI)⁸⁷, Office of the Prosecutor General of Ukraine (OGPU)⁸⁸

The European Union has the highest number of open cases – 1,220 cases, with a conviction rate of 62%. In the United States, 870 cases were opened, and the effectiveness of law enforcement demonstrates a high level of 78%. The UK has 340 cases with a 70% success rate. In Ukraine, the figure is somewhat lower – 495 cases, with a rather low percentage of convictions – only 41%. This difference is indicative of problems in the national law enforcement and judicial systems, particularly in terms of evidence collection and procedural support.

To compare the scale of financial losses from crimes in the field of public resources, a pie chart is provided (Figure 2).

⁸² European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF). (2024). *Id.*

⁸³ European Public Prosecutor's Office (EPPO). (2024). *Id.*

⁸⁴ U.S. Department of Justice. (2023). *Id.*

⁸⁵ U.S. Office of Inspector General. (2023). *Id.*

⁸⁶ National Anti-Corruption Bureau of Ukraine (NABU). (2023). *Id.*

⁸⁷ State Bureau of Investigation of Ukraine (SBI). (2023). *Id.*

⁸⁸ Office of the Prosecutor General of Ukraine (OGPU). (2023). *Id.*

Figure 2. The structure of the average amount of losses from the misuse of public resources in the EU, the US, the UK and Ukraine (2023)

Source: Created by the author on the basis of European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF)⁸⁹, European Public Prosecutor's Office (EPPO)⁹⁰, U.S. Department of Justice⁹¹, U.S. Office of Inspector General⁹², National Anti-Corruption Bureau of Ukraine (NABU)⁹³, State Bureau of Investigation of Ukraine (SBI)⁹⁴, Office of the Prosecutor General of Ukraine (OGPU)⁹⁵

The largest average loss amount was recorded in the United States – \$6.2 million, which is 38% of the total distribution across the four countries. The European Union is in second place with an average of EUR 4.5 million (28%). In the United Kingdom, the average loss amounted to £3.1 million (19%), while in Ukraine it was €2.4 million (15%). This differentiation indicates that the largest crimes in terms of losses are recorded in more economically developed jurisdictions with large budgetary flows, but in Ukraine, due to weak control and transparency, there are also significant risks of financial losses, albeit at a slightly lower level in terms of absolute value.

Let us consider practical proposals for improving criminal legislation and law enforcement practice in Ukraine, taking into account international trends:

1. Introduce the institution of criminal liability of legal entities for violations in the use of public resources. International experience^{96, 97} shows the effectiveness of bringing not only individuals but also legal entities to criminal liability for misuse of public funds. In Ukraine, it is advisable to legislate mechanisms for bringing legal entities to justice, in particular for participation in illegal public procurement and financial manipulation.

⁸⁹ European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF). (2024). *Id.*

⁹⁰ European Public Prosecutor's Office (EPPO). (2024). *Id.*

⁹¹ U.S. Department of Justice. (2023). *Id.*

⁹² U.S. Office of Inspector General. (2023). *Id.*

⁹³ National Anti-Corruption Bureau of Ukraine (NABU). (2023). *Id.*

⁹⁴ State Bureau of Investigation of Ukraine (SBI). (2023). *Id.*

⁹⁵ Office of the Prosecutor General of Ukraine (OGPU). (2023). *Id.*

⁹⁶ Souto, M. A. (2022). *Id.*

⁹⁷ Allegrezza, S., & Bruzzese, G. (2025). *Id.*

2. Developing clear criteria for distinguishing between criminal acts and violations of financial discipline. In Ukrainian practice, there is often a problem of misclassification of acts⁹⁸. The amount of damage, the nature of the intent, and other objective signs should be defined in law to clearly distinguish a crime from an administrative offense.

3. Create a unified state online register of violations related to the use of state resources, with open access to information on cases and their results. Openness of information, as the practice of the EU countries shows⁹⁹, contributes to the effectiveness of control and prevention of repeated violations. Such a register in Ukraine would allow the public and controlling authorities to track the use of budget funds in real time.

4. Mandatory implementation of the system of internal compliance and anti-corruption audits in all state institutions and state-owned enterprises. According to the experience of the United States and the United Kingdom^{100, 101} compliance programs are an effective tool for preventing offenses. In Ukraine, it is necessary to enshrine in law the obligation to conduct regular internal audits and prepare anti-corruption reports.

3. DISCUSSION

The results of the study show that the application of criminal liability for the misuse of public resources in Ukraine remains inconsistent and requires significant improvement. The findings confirm the conclusions of such researchers as Allegrezza and Bruzzese¹⁰², Souto¹⁰³, who emphasize the importance of implementing international legal standards in national legislation to improve the effectiveness of law enforcement. At the same time, some authors believe that Ukraine's legal framework already contains sufficient tools to combat such crimes, and the main problem is the ineffectiveness of their practical application^{104, 105}.

One of the key controversial issues in the scientific literature is the need for criminal liability of legal entities. Some researchers argue that without the introduction of such an institution, it is impossible to fully prosecute organizations that

⁹⁸ Makarenko, O. Y., Makarenko, N. A., Nazymko, O. V., Hromenko, Y. O., & Nesterenko, K. O. (2021). *Id.*

⁹⁹ European Parliament & Council of the European Union. (2013). *Id.*

¹⁰⁰ U.S. Department of Justice. (2023). *Id.*

¹⁰¹ A Borovyk, A. V. (2020). *Id.*

¹⁰² Allegrezza, S., & Bruzzese, G. (2025). *Id.*

¹⁰³ Souto, M. A. (2022). *Id.*

¹⁰⁴ Kuzmenko, O., Koval, S., & Koval, V. (2021). *Id.*

¹⁰⁵ Movchan, R. O., Dudorov, O. O., Vozniuk, A. A., Areshonkov, V. Yu., & Lutsenko, Yu. V. (2021). *Id.*

systematically misuse public funds^{106, 107}. On the other hand, there is an opinion that legal entities should be held accountable mainly in the administrative and legal sphere, as criminal prosecution of corporations can lead to an excessive burden on the judicial system^{108, 109}. The results of our study suggest that criminal liability of legal entities is necessary, as the lack of clear mechanisms in this area leaves a significant part of violations in the field of public resources unpunished.

The role of transparency and safeguards is another subject of scientific debate. Researchers Blinova¹¹⁰ and Lee¹¹¹ emphasize that the introduction of digital tools for monitoring public funds helps to reduce the risk of their misuse. At the same time, other researchers¹¹² emphasize that transparency is only an auxiliary tool, while effective investigations and criminal prosecution remain the key. Our results confirm that the combination of transparency, digital audit, and effective control can be the basis for minimizing financial crime.

The issue of distinguishing between criminal offenses and administrative violations remains problematic. Some authors propose to legislate the distinction criteria based on the amount of damage and intent^{113,114}. Our research shows that a balance is needed between clear legislative guidelines and the possibility of individualized case assessment.

The study also confirms the problem of insufficient coordination between investigating authorities and auditors, which was previously emphasized by Khalizov¹¹⁵ and Demchuk and Lenger¹¹⁶. This problem leads to delays in investigations and loss of evidence, so the creation of a single integrated information system is one of the important areas for improving law enforcement practice.

To summarize, it is worth noting that the findings are partially consistent with the research hypothesis that national criminal legislation needs to be reformed in line with international standards and experience. However, the problems of inconsistency in the mechanisms of interaction between law enforcement agencies and unclear legislative

¹⁰⁶ Al-Kayid, J. H., El-Manaseer, S. A., Al Khawatreh, A. M., & Ibra-him, A. A. (2023). *Id.*

¹⁰⁷ Giannini, A., & Kwik, J. (2023). *Id.*

¹⁰⁸ Borovyk, A. V. (2020). *Id.*

¹⁰⁹ Makarenko, O. Y., Makarenko, N. A., Nazymko, O. V., Hromenko, Y. O., & Nesterenko, K. O. (2021). *Id.*

¹¹⁰ Blinova, H. O. (2021). *Id.*

¹¹¹ Lee, J. M. (2013). *Id.*

¹¹² Kuzmenko, O., Koval, S., & Koval, V. (2021). *Id.*

¹¹³ Nikolinakos, N. Th. (2024). *Id.*

¹¹⁴ Pekarchuk, V. M., & Chaika, V. Yu. (2020). *Id.*

¹¹⁵ Khalizov, D. V. (2024). *Id.*

¹¹⁶ Demchuk, A. M., & Lenger, Y. I. (2024). *Id.*

criteria for distinguishing between violations remain unresolved. These aspects require further comprehensive research and legislative initiatives.

CONCLUSION

5

The findings of the study suggest that the criminal law mechanism for combating the misuse of public resources in Ukraine is still in its infancy and lags far behind the best international practices. It is determined that the problem lies not only in the imperfection of legislation, but also in the poor efficiency of its implementation due to the lack of comprehensive interagency cooperation and systemic transparency. The practical approaches proposed by the study, in particular, the introduction of criminal liability of legal entities and the creation of a single open register of violations, should become the basis for reforming the legislative framework and law enforcement practice. An unexpected but revealing result of the study was the discovery of a high disproportion in the ratio of the number of cases initiated and brought to a verdict in Ukraine compared to the EU and the USA, which indicates the depth of problems in the field of investigation and evidence. The practical significance of the work lies in the formulation of specific proposals for legislative initiatives and modernization of control mechanisms. The main limitation of the study was the lack of complete open statistics on individual government agencies of Ukraine, which requires additional empirical research. In the future, it is of scientific interest to develop an effective model of criminal liability of legal entities, to study the impact of digital technologies on the transparency of public spending, and to assess the effectiveness of compliance programs in the public sector. It is recommended that further research should focus on a comparative legal analysis of the legislation of countries with the highest rates of successful investigations, as well as on the practical testing of internal control mechanisms in Ukrainian public institutions.

References

1. Allegrezza, S., & Bruzzese, G. (2025). Supervision and enforcement of EU's anti-money-laundering and countering the financing of terrorism. In R. D'Ambrosio, et al. (Eds.), *EU banking and capital markets regulation* (pp. 487–521). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70529-8_14
2. Antoniuk, N. O. (2020). Means of differentiation of criminal liability. *Law of Ukraine*, 2020(2), 228–245. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340097968_Zasobi_diferenciacii_kriminalnoi_vidpovidalnosti
3. Blinova, H. O. (2021). Legal foundations for the use of electronic information resources in the concept of a digital state. *Problems of Modern Transformations*.

- Series: *Law, Public Governance and Administration*, 2, 53–60.
<https://doi.org/10.54929/pmtl-issue2-2021-10>
4. Borovyk, A. V. (2020). European standards of criminal liability for corruption offenses and their prevention. *Actual Problems of State and Law*, 85, 5–12. <https://doi.org/10.32837/apdp.v0i85.1820>
 5. Demchuk, A. M., & Lenger, Y. I. (2024). Administrative and criminal liability for environmental offenses in the field of land relations. *New Ukrainian Law*, 5, 67–73. <https://doi.org/10.51989/NUL.2024.5.8>
 6. European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF). (2024). OLAF report 2023: Protecting the EU's financial interests. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://ec.europa.eu/anti-fraud>
 7. European Public Prosecutor's Office (EPPO). (2024). *Annual report 2023*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://www.eppo.europa.eu>
 8. Giannini, A., & Kwik, J. (2023). Negligence failures and negligence fixes: A comparative analysis of criminal regulation of AI and autonomous vehicles. *Criminal Law Forum*, 34(1), 43–85. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10609-023-09451-1>
 9. Khalizov, D. V. (2024). On the issue of administrative liability for violations of legislation in the field of land use by farms. *Bulletin of the Criminological Association of Ukraine*, 2(32), 896–903. <https://doi.org/10.32631/vca.2024.2.69>
 10. Klein, G., Assadi, D., & Zwilling, M. (2024). Fighting fire with fire: Combating criminal abuse of cryptocurrency with a P2P mindset. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 26(4), 123–145. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-024-10498-7>
 11. Kuzmenko, O., Koval, S., & Koval, V. (2021). Criminal liability of legal entities for environmental crimes: Problems of law enforcement practice. *Cuestiones Políticas*, 39(70), 621–636. <https://doi.org/10.46398/cuestpol.3970.52>
 12. Lee, J. M. (2013). Criminal liability for misappropriation of university-industry cooperation funds: Supreme Court decision 2009Do13751 rendered on October 13, 2011. *Journal of Law and Politics Research*, 13(2), 123–145. https://www.kci.go.kr/kciportal/landing/article.kci?arti_id=ART001790863
 13. Makarenko, O. Y., Makarenko, N. A., Nazymko, O. V., Hromenko, Y. O., & Nesterenko, K. O. (2021). Problematic issues of criminal prosecution for the illegal extraction of mineral resources. *Scientific Bulletin of National Mining University*, 2021(4), 139–145. <https://doi.org/10.33271/nvngu/2021-4/139>
 14. Movchan, R. O., Dudorov, O. O., Vozniuk, A. A., Areshonkov, V. Yu., & Lutsenko, Yu. V. (2021). Combating commodity smuggling in Ukraine: In search of the optimal legislative model. *Amazonia Investiga*, 10(47), 142–151. <https://doi.org/10.34069/AI/2021.47.11.14>
 15. National Anti-Corruption Bureau of Ukraine (NABU). (2023). *Annual report*. Retrieved from <https://nabu.gov.ua>
 16. Nikolinakos, N. Th. (2024). Adapting EU liability rules to the digital age and artificial intelligence: The European Commission's 2021 inception impact assessment. In *Adapting the EU civil liability regime to the digital age: Artificial*

- intelligence, robotics, and other emerging technologies* (pp. 253–326). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-67969-8_6
17. Office of the Prosecutor General of Ukraine (OGPU). (2023). Annual statistical report. <https://gp.gov.ua>
 18. Pekarchuk, V. M., & Chaika, V. Yu. (2020). Problems of legal liability for infringement on state symbols. *South Ukrainian Law Journal*, 3(1), 103–115. <https://doi.org/10.32755/sjcriminal.2020.01.103>
 19. Rembert, D. A., Joseph, J. J., Threadcraft-Walker, W., Thread-craft, M., Brown, D., Soyele, O. E., & Henderson, H. (2023). Criminal liability for correctional officer excessive use of force. *Crime, Law and Social Change*, 79(2), 105–128. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10611-022-10036-z>
 20. State Bureau of Investigation of Ukraine (SBI). (2023). Annual report. <https://dbr.gov.ua>
 21. U.S. Department of Justice. (2023). *Annual report on fraud and misuse of public funds*. <https://www.justice.gov>
 22. U.S. Office of Inspector General. (2023). *Semiannual report to Congress*. <https://www.oig.gov>
 23. United Nations. (2003). *United Nations Convention against Corruption*. <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/corruption/uncac.html>

Books

1. Al-Kayid, J. H., El-Manaseer, S. A., Al Khawatreh, A. M., & Ibra-him, A. A. (2023). Reflections on the impact of digital transformation on criminal policy. In E. A. ElTayeb, et al. (Eds.), *Artificial intelligence (AI) and finance* (pp. 120–133). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-39158-3_11
2. Foti, D., & Malino, E. (2024). Third Parties in Italian Criminal Proceedings. In S. Ruggeri, et al. (Eds), *Third Parties in Criminal Proceedings. Legal Studies in International, European and Comparative Criminal Law, Vol 10*. Springer, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-73970-5>
3. Lanz, M., & Mijic, S. (2023). Risks associated with the use of natural language generation: Swiss civil liability law perspective. In E. Schweighofer, et al. (Eds.), *Multidisciplinary perspectives on artificial intelligence and the law* (pp. 297–314). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-41264-6_17
4. Souto, M. A. (2022). Money laundering, cybercrime and criminal responsibility of legal persons. In Y. Liu, et al. (Eds.), *Cybercrimes and financial crimes in the global era* (pp. 145–164). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-3189-5_16

Laws

1. Council of Europe. (1999). *Criminal Law Convention on Corruption* (ETS No. 173). <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list?module=treaty-detail&treaty-num=173>

2. European Parliament, & Council of the European Union. (2013). Regulation (EU) No 883/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 September 2013 concerning investigations conducted by the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF). *Official Journal of the European Union*, L248, 1–22. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32013R0883>
3. U.S. Congress. (2009). *Fraud Enforcement and Recovery Act of 2009*, Public Law, 111–21. <https://www.congress.gov/111/plaws/publ21/PLAW-111publ21.pdf>
4. Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. (2001). *Criminal Code of Ukraine* No. 2341-III of April 5 2021 (as amended). <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2341-14#Text>